

%% 载入Homer2 预处理后的*.nirs文件，并对各个被试各个条件的 HRF 及可用通道进行整理

%注意这个路径中只能包含预处理好的.nirs文件，不能包含预处理过程其他不同的文件

```
datadir = 'C:data\nirs';
```

%使用dir 函数筛选在 datadir 路径下所有.nirs 格式的数据

```
dirinfo = dir(fullfile(datadir, '*.nirs'));
```

%提取数据的文件名信息

```
file_names = {dirinfo.name};
```

%导入第 subj 个被试的信息

```
for subj = 1:length(file_names)
```

```
    %读取.nirs文件
```

```
    load(strcat(datadir, '\,file_names{1,subj}'),'-mat')
```

```
    %保存 procResult.dc 变量
```

```
    %procResult.dc 是 3D 数据：时间*类型(HBO,HBR,HBT)*通道
```

```
    alldc(:,:,:) = procResult.dc;
```

```
    alldc_all{subj,1} = alldc;
```

```
    clear alldc
```

```
end
```

```
save alldc_all.mat alldc_all
```

%% 提取 evt 和 mark 数据

```
clc;clear all
```

%同上，使用dir 函数筛选在 datadir 路径下所有.evt 格式的数据

```
datadir = 'C:data\nirs';
```

```
dirinfo = dir(fullfile(datadir, '*.evt'));
```

```
file_names = {dirinfo.name};
```

```
for subj = 1:length(file_names)
```

```
    %读取.evt文件
```

```
    mark=load(strcat(datadir, '\,file_names{1,subj}'));
```

```
    %保存每位被试的 mark 信息
```

```
    mark_z{subj,1} = mark;
```

```
    clear mark
```

```
end
```

%转换为相应的 mark 编号

```
for subj = 1:size(mark_z,1)
```

```
    for num = 1:size(mark_z{subj,1},1)
```

```

a2 = mark_z{subj,1}(num,2);
a3 = mark_z{subj,1}(num,3);
a4 = mark_z{subj,1}(num,4);
a5 = mark_z{subj,1}(num,5);
a6 = mark_z{subj,1}(num,6);
a7 = mark_z{subj,1}(num,7);
a8 = mark_z{subj,1}(num,8);
a9 = mark_z{subj,1}(num,9);
a10 = a2 + a3*2 + a4*4 + a5*8 + a6*16 + a7*32 + a8*64 + a9*128 ;
mark_z{subj,1}(num,10) = a10;
end
end
clear a2 a3 a4 a5 a6 a7 a8 a9 a10

```

```

save mark_z.mat mark_z

```

```

%% 提取特定 HbO/Hb/HbT 数据

```

```

clc;clear all

```

```

load alldc_all.mat

```

```

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```

```

for subj = 1:length(alldc_all)

```

```

    %构造数据 提取 dc 的所有时间 第 1 个血氧浓度类型的 所有通道的数据

```

```

    %也可选择自己想要的通道时可以将最后一个冒号改为[] []里面放上自己想要的通道数 用空格或逗号隔开

```

```

    oxyData=squeeze(alldc_all{subj,1}(:,1,:));

```

```

    oxyData_all{subj,1} = oxyData;

```

```

end

```

```

save oxyData_all.mat oxyData_all

```

```

%%

```

```

clc;clear all

```

```

load oxyData_all.mat

```

```

load mark_all.mat

```

```

for subj = 1:size(oxyData_all,1)

```

```

    for ch = 1:size(oxyData_all{subj,1},2)

```

```

        for num = 1:size(mark_z{subj,1},1)

```

```

            if mark_z{subj,1}(num,10) == 2

```

```

                data_Zpreteaching

```

```

oxyData_all{subj,1}(mark_z{subj,1}(num,1):mark_z{subj,1}(num+1,1),ch);

```

```

                data_Zpreteaching_all{subj,ch} = data_Zpreteaching;

```

=

```

elseif mark_z{subj,1}(num,10) ==6
    data_Fpreteaching
oxyData_all{subj,1}(mark_z{subj,1}(num,1):mark_z{subj,1}(num+1,1),ch);
    data_Fpreteaching_all{subj,ch} = data_Fpreteaching;
end
end
end
end

```

```

for subj = 1:size(oxyData_all,1)
    for ch = 1:size(oxyData_all{subj,1},2)
        for num = 1:size(mark_z{subj,1},1)
            if mark_z{subj,1}(num,10) ==8
                data_Fpostteaching
oxyData_all{subj,1}(mark_z{subj,1}(num,1):mark_z{subj,1}(num+1,1),ch);
                data_Fpostteaching_all{subj,ch} = data_Fhouteaching;
            end
        end
    end
end

```

```

for subj = 1:size(oxyData_all,1)
    for ch = 1:size(oxyData_all{subj,1},2)
        for num = 1:size(mark_z{subj,1},1)
            if mark_z{subj,1}(num,10) ==5
                data_Zpostteaching
oxyData_all{subj,1}(mark_z{subj,1}(num,1):mark_z{subj,1}(num+1,1),ch);
                data_Zpostteaching_all{subj,ch} = data_Zhouteaching;
            end
        end
    end
end

```

```

for subj = 1:size(data_Zpreteaching_all,1)
    for ch = 1:size(data_Zpreteaching_all,2)
        data_Zpreteaching = mean(data_Zpreteaching_all{subj,ch});
        data_Zpreteaching_mean(subj,ch) = data_Zpreteaching;
    end
end

```

```

for subj = 1:size(data_Fpreteaching_all,1)

```

```

for ch = 1:size(data_Fpreteaching_all,2)
data_Fpreteaching = mean(data_Fpreteaching_all{subj,ch});
data_Fpreteaching_mean(subj,ch) = data_Fpreteaching;
end
end

```

```

for subj = 1:size(data_Zpostteaching_all,1)
for ch = 1:size(data_Zpostteaching_all,2)
data_Zpostteaching = mean(data_Zpostteaching_all{subj,ch});
data_Zpostteaching_mean(subj,ch) = data_Zpostteaching;
end
end
for subj = 1:size(data_Fpostteaching_all,1)
for ch = 1:size(data_Fpostteaching_all,2)
data_Fpostteaching = mean(data_Fpostteaching_all{subj,ch});
data_Fpostteaching_mean(subj,ch) = data_Fpostteaching;
end
end
end

```

```

for subj = 1:size(data_Zpreteaching_mean,1)
for ch = 1:size(data_Zpreteaching_mean,2)
r = data_Zpreteaching_mean(subj,ch);
r_new = atanh(r);
data_Zpreteaching_mean_z(subj,ch) = r_new;
end
end
for subj = 1:size(data_Fpreteaching_mean,1)
for ch = 1:size(data_Fpreteaching_mean,2)
r = data_Fpreteaching_mean(subj,ch);
r_new = atanh(r);
data_Fpreteaching_mean_z(subj,ch) = r_new;
end
end
for subj = 1:size(data_Zpostteaching_mean,1)
for ch = 1:size(data_Zpostteaching_mean,2)
r = data_Zpostteaching_mean(subj,ch);
r_new = atanh(r);
data_Zpostteaching_mean_z(subj,ch) = r_new;
end
end
for subj = 1:size(data_Fpostteaching_mean,1)
for ch = 1:size(data_Fpostteaching_mean,2)

```

```
r = data_Fpostteaching_mean(subj,ch);
r_new = atanh(r);
data_Fpostteaching_mean_z(subj,ch) = r_new;
end
end
```

```
[h,p1,ci,stats] = ttest(data_Zpreteaching_mean_z,data_Zpostteaching_mean_z);
```

```
p_fdr1 = mafdr(p1, 'BHFDR', true);
```

```
[h,p2,ci,stats] = ttest(data_Fpreteaching_mean_z,data_Fpostteaching_mean_z);
```

```
p_fdr2= mafdr(p2, 'BHFDR', true);
```

```
[h,p3,ci,stats] =
ttest2(data_Lecture_teaching_Zpostteaching_mean_z,data_Body_teaching_Zpostteac
hing_mean_z);
p_fdr3= mafdr(p3, 'BHFDR', true);
[h,p4,ci,stats] =
ttest2(data_Lecture_teaching_Fpostteaching_mean_z,data_Body_teaching_Fpostteac
hing_mean_z);
p_fdr4= mafdr(p4, 'BHFDR', true);
```